

**A STUDY OF PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT OF TEACHER
EDUCATORS OF MUMBAI**

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Abstract

A teacher is the key figure in the building of a nation. The task of a teacher is transaction of knowledge, imparting the skill and inculcation of values. The role of a teacher is very important for the development of the child. Unless the country has persons of proper temperament and ability as teachers, it cannot have citizens of great vision and character. Teacher education programmes prepare future teachers for lifelong learning and professionalism. To be professionals, teachers require a foundation of professional knowledge upon which to base instructional decisions. The teacher education programmes would remain incomplete without specific competencies and a high degree of professional commitment among teacher educators. Therefore It's important to identify the various dimensions of professional commitment of teacher's educators. The present study focuses on the professional commitment of teacher educators and its dimensions . This study was conducted on 30 teacher educators from the 6 B.ED Colleges of Mumbai affiliated to Mumbai University. The study adopted the descriptive survey method . It was found that the professional commitment level of teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is near to higher scale.

Key Words: *Professional Commitment, Teacher Educators, B.Ed colleges.*

Introduction

Teaching is classified as profession. Teaching is no simply an occupation aimed at making money for livelihood but it is a social service for national development. A teacher should be permanently committed to his work. Those who have chosen teaching as profession, acquire necessary knowledge and skills with no personal likes and dislikes. Professional commitment means the feeling of dedication among the individuals of a group towards their profession. This commitment area involves two essential components namely-pride in one's being in the teaching profession and a strong desire for professional development. Teachers 'total

involvement and devotion is must for empowering the students. During and even after school hours, a committed teacher's mind remains always occupied with thoughts of children, their growth, individually as well as collectively and improvement of their performance.

The importance of the quality of teachers should be overemphasized because the strength and success of an educational system depends on them whether they teach in schools, colleges or universities. Actually the quality of a nation depends on the quality of its citizens, quality of citizens depends on the quality of their education and quality of education depends on the quality of their teachers. As professionals, teachers must base decisions on systematic knowledge and foster enquiry and the discovery of new knowledge.

According to **Patanker** (1999) teachers shape the destiny of the nation in the classroom. They develop societies, indicate path of progress to the nation, and sustain the human aspects of existence. They nurture and cultivate humanistic, ethical and moral values among pupils.

According to **Madhuri Shah** (1994) The teacher has an important, vital role to play in efforts to relate education to national development and social change. It is the responsibly of the teacher to guide and inspire students, to enrich his discipline, to inculcate values, which are in consonance with our cultural heritage and our social objectives.

A teacher education programmes prepares a teacher as more mature and confident to perform his /her task more efficiently. Proper education to the teacher enables him to have knowledge of how children grow, develop and learn, how they can be taught effectively and how their inner potentialities can be brought and developed.

Dictionary of education **C.V.Good** (1973), defines teacher education as "All formal and in-formal activities and experience that help to qualify a person to assume the responsibility as a member of the educational profession or to discharge his responsibilities most effectively".

The National Council of Teacher Education (NCTE) came into being as a statutory organization in 1993 with a mandate to regulate teacher education in the country.

Three levels i.e. Pre-primary Teacher Education, Elementary Teacher Education and Secondary Teacher Education.

Meyer et al. (1993) defined three distinct components of professional commitment:

- Affective Professional Commitment (APC)
- Continuance Professional Commitment (CPC)
- Normative Professional Commitment (NPC)

Affective Professional Commitment (APC) refers to identification with, involvement in, and emotional attachment to the profession. Thus, employees with strong affective professional commitment remain members of their profession because they want to do so. For example, professionals with a strong sense of affective commitment to their profession will keep up with developments in their profession subscribe to trade journals, attend professional meetings, and participate in their professional association.

Continuance Professional Commitment (CPC) refers to commitment based on the employee's recognition of the costs associated with leaving their profession. Employees with strong continuance commitment remain with their profession because they realize that they have much to lose by not doing so. Professionals with high levels of continuance commitments might be less inclined to involve themselves in professional activities other than those required to retain membership of their profession (Mayer et al., 1993).

Normative Professional Commitment (NPC) refers to commitment based on a sense of obligation to the profession. An employee with strong normative professional commitment remains a member of their profession because they feel they ought to do so. Normative professional commitment may

develops because of effective professional socialisation or sacrifices involved in becoming a member of a particular profession.

Need of the Study

The need of the present study is to measure and assess commitment level of teacher educators towards their profession of teacher's training. Colleges of Education prepare teachers to teach at secondary level and senior secondary level of education. At this level, we have Government financing institutions of Education and self-financing colleges of education affiliated to the various universities. Teacher educators are like a burning lamp having burning oil for lighting the mind and hearts of pupil-teachers. To provide quality teacher education at the elementary and secondary level, teacher-educators have to maintain a high level of academic and professional competence so as to prepare the best teachers for our country's schools. Unless, teacher educators are in a position to provide worthwhile experiences to our pupil teachers for realizing the stipulated teacher education objectives related to a particular type of teacher education course, the talk of any worthwhile quality teacher education would be futile by all means. At this juncture of time, where unprecedented changes of knowledge and action manifest in all the diversions of worldly life, the role of teacher educators needs to take a positive direction therefore researcher wanted to study the professional commitment level of teacher educators.

Definition of the Terms

Conceptual Definition

Professional Commitment: A person who belongs to a profession being bound emotionally/intellectually to a course of action or to another person/other persons. (Oxford Dictionary)

Teacher Educators:

A person that educates, especially a teacher, principal, or other person involved in planning or directing education of teachers. (Dictionary.com)

B.Ed.Colleges:An institution of higher learning, especially one providing a professional training to teachers. (Dictionary.com)

Operational Definition

Professional Commitment :Refers to dedication, promise of teacher educators to behave and act according to certain established and well-accepted rules and norms, concerning mainly with student-teachers, society, profession, quest to achieve excellence and basic human values

Teacher Educators :A person who gives instruction and education to future teachers.

B.Ed. College :An institution under Mumbai University where training of teachers is carried out.

Aim Of The Study

To Study the professional commitment Of teacher educators of Mumbai.

Objectives Of The Study

- 1.To study the professional commitment of teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai .
- 2.To find out the professional commitment of teacher educators :
(a) to the learner (b) to the Society (c) to the Profession (d) to achieve excellence for professional actions and (e) commitment to basic values.
- 3.To compare the professional commitment of teacher educators to the learner and society.
- 4.To compare the professional commitment of teacher educators to the society and profession.

Methodology Of the Study

For the present study, the researcher has used the descriptive method of quantitative type research. The data collected were in the form of numbers.

Sample size and sampling technique

This study has a sample size of 30 teacher educators from the 6 B.ED. Colleges of

Mumbai affiliated to Mumbai University. For ensuring valid and accurate results, Random sampling was employed. The researcher covered different areas of Mumbai city to get a fair view of the teacher educators.

Data Collection tool

The researcher has used readymade tool by Dr. Vishal Sood, Principal of Abhilashi P.G. College of Education Nerchowk, Distt.Mandi (H.P). Professional Commitment Scale for Teacher Educators (PCSTE) was developed and devised by employing the 'method of summated ratings' in which each item has to be rated on a five point psychological continuum (rating scale) i.e. Always, Frequently, Sometimes, Rarely and Never. The total professional commitment score in respect of a teacher educator is the sum total of his/her ratings on all statements/items of the scale. This tool has 70 items and five dimensions i.e. Commitment to the learner, Commitment to the Society, Commitment to the Profession, Commitment to Achieve Excellence for Professional Actions and Commitment to Basic Values.

Scoring Pattern

Professional Commitment Scale for Teacher Educators comprised of total 70 items. Sixty five items are positively worded and five items with serial numbers 6, 9, 36, 40 and 68. Which are negatively worded these items were developed in statement form with five point rating scale. The scoring of items is done in such a manner that if the answer to a item is 'Always', a score of 5 is given; for 'frequently' option, a score of 4; for 'sometimes' alternative, a score of 3; for 'Rarely' option, a score of 2 and for 'Never' option, a score of 1 is answered. On the contrary, in case of negative items, the above scoring procedure is reversed completely.

Analysis of the study

In the present study researcher has used descriptive analysis. The statistical technique used as Mean and Standard deviation. Descriptive statistics include the numbers, tablets, charts and graphs used to describe, organize, summarize and present raw data.

Objective 1: To study the professional commitment of the teacher educators of B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai.

Figure No. 01: Showing graphical representation of Overall Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators

Interpretation:

From the above data we can observe that the overall mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai are 4.1 and 0.9 respectively. **The above data and graphical representation indicates that the overall professional commitment of teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is near to higher scale.**

OBJECTIVE 2 (a): To find out the professional commitment of teacher educators to the learner

Table No. 1: Showing Mean and Standard Deviation of the professional commitment of teacher educators to the learner of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to the learner	61.8	5.8

Figure No. 02: Showing graphical representation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the Learner.

Interpretation:

From the above data we can observe that mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators to the learner of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 61.8 and 5.8 and respectively which means Commitment scale will range from $(61.8-5.8=56.0)$ to $(61.8+5.8=67.6)$. **The above data and graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the Learner of different B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 95.21 to 78.87 percentage which depicts good commitment level on the scale.**

OBJECTIVE 2 (b): To study the professional commitment of teacher educators to the society.

Table No. 2: Showing Mean and Standard Deviation of the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the society of B.Ed. College of Mumbai.

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to the Society	55.6	7.3

Figure No. 03: Showing graphical representation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the Society

Interpretation:

From the above data we can observe that the mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators to the society of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 55.6 and 7.3 and respectively which means Commitment scale will range from $(55.6-7.3=48.3)$ to $(55.6+7.3=62.9)$. Percentage scale will range from 89.85 to 69.0. The above data and graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of 30 teacher educators to the society of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 89.85 to 69.0 percentage which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.

OBJECTIVE 2 (c) To find out professional commitment of teacher educator to the profession

Table No. 3: Showing Mean and Standard Deviation of the Professional Commitment of teacher Educators to the Profession of B.Ed. College of Mumbai

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to the Profession	57.0	5.9

Figure No. 04: Showing graphical representation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the Profession

Interpretation:

From the above data we can observe that mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators to the profession of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 57.0 and 5.9 and respectively which means Commitment scale will range from $(57.0 - 5.9 = 51.1)$ to $(57.0 + 5.9 = 62.9)$. Percentage scale will range from 100.7 to 80.76. The above data and graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the profession of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 100.7 to 80.76 percentage which depicts very good Commitment level on the scale.

OBJECTIVE 2 (d): To study professional commitment of teacher educator to achieve excellence for professional actions

Table no. 4: Showing mean and standard deviation of the professional commitment of teacher educators to achieve excellence for professional actions.

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to Achieve excellence for professional actions	59.0	6.5

Figure No. 05: Showing graphical representation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to achieve excellence for professional actions.

Interpretation: From the above data we can observe that mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators to achieve excellence for professional actions of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 59.0 and 6.5 and respectively which means Commitment scale will range from $(59.0-6.5=52.5)$ to $(59.0+6.5=65.5)$. Percentage scale will range from 92.2 to 73.94. The above data and graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to achieve excellence for professional actions of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 92.2 to 73.94. percentage which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.

OBJECTIVE 2 (e): To study professional commitment of teacher educator to basic values

Table No.5: Showing Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of teacher Educators to basic Values

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to Basic values	52.2	4.8

Figure No. 06: Showing graphical representation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to Basic Values.

Interpretation:

From the above data we can observe that mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of teacher educators to Basic Values of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 52.2 and 4.8 and respectively which means Commitment scale will range from $(52.2-4.8=47.4)$ to $(52.2+4.8=57.0)$. Percentage scale will range from 95 to 79. The above data and graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of 30 teacher educators to Basic Values of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 95 to 79 . Percentage which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.

OBJECTIVE 3 : To compare professional commitment of teacher educator to the learner and society

Table No. 6: Showing Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the learner and to the society.

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to the learner	61.8	5.8
Commitment to the Society	55.6	7.3

Figure No. 07: Showing graphical representation of comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the Learner and to the society.

Interpretation:

From above data and graphical representation we can observe comparison of mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of 30 teacher educators to learner and to society of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 61.8 ,5.8 and 55.6 , 7.3 respectively. **The above data and Graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the learner is more as compare to the society of B.Ed. College of Mumbai.**

OBJECTIVE 4: To compare the professional commitment of teacher educators to the society and profession

Table No. 7: Showing Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the Society and to the Profession.

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Commitment to the society	55.6	7.3
Commitment to the Profession	57.0	5.9

Figure No. 08: Showing graphical representation of comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators to the society and to the profession.

Interpretation:

From above data and graphical representation we can observe comparison of mean and standard deviation of professional commitment of 30 teacher educators to the society and to the profession of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is 55.6 , 7.3 and 57.0 , 5.9 respectively. **The above data and Graphical representation indicates that the Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the Profession is more as compare to the society of B.Ed. College of Mumbai.**

Major Findings

On the basis of the analysis and interpretations the following findings have been drawn out-

- The overall professional commitment level of teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is near to higher scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the Learner of different B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 95.21 to 78.87 % which depicts good commitment level on the scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the society of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 89.85 to 69.0 % which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the profession of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 100.7 to 80.76 % which depicts very good Commitment level on the scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to achieve excellence for professional actions of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 92.2 to 73.94. % which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to basic values of different B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai is ranging from 95 to 79. % which depicts good Commitment level on the scale.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the learner is more as compare to the society of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai.
- The Professional Commitment of teacher educators to the Profession is more as compared to the society of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai.

Conclusions

From the above findings it can be concluded that overall Professional Commitment of the teacher educators of B.Ed. Colleges of Mumbai towards dimensions such as commitment to the learner, society, profession, achieving excellence for professional

actions is very good but when it comes to the dimension of commitment towards basic values it shows a decrease, which means the teacher educators are comparatively less committed towards basic values.

Suggestions: To the Teacher Educators-

Teaching is considered as one of the oldest profession as well as a noble profession and to improve education and strengthen the teaching profession teachers' commitment is important and this commitment can be achieved when teachers will get good training from the institution which can be possible when teacher educators will be more committed towards their profession. Based on the findings of this research and understanding of the study it is suggested to the teacher educators of B.Ed. colleges of Mumbai to show an equal commitment to the basic values.

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